

CHARACTERISTICS AND DEVELOPMENT WAYS OF ELECTRONIC COMMERCE ACTIVITY

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola iqtisodiyotni erkinlashtirish sharoitida internet orqali elektron tijorat hamda raqamli iqtisodiyotning asosi bo'lgan muammolar bilan bog'liq masalalar, raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tish mexanizmi, elektron tijorat haqida nazariy va amaliy ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Аннотация

В этой статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с электронной коммерцией через интернет, а также проблемы, в основе цифровой экономики в условиях либерализации экономики, механизма перехода к цифровой экономике, а также дается теоретическая и практическая информация об электронной коммерции.

Annotation

This article provides theoretical and practical information on issues related to the problems that underlie e-commerce and digital economy through the internet in the context of liberalization of the economy, the mechanism of transition to digital economy, e-commerce.

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli mahsulotlar, elektron savdo maydonchasi, elektron savdo maydonchasining operatori, elektron tijorat operatori, elektron tijorat subyektlari*

Ключевые слова: *цифровые продукты, электронная торговая площадка, оператор электронной торговой площадки, электронная коммерция, оператор электронной коммерции, субъекты электронной коммерции.*

Keywords: *digital products, electronic trading platform, electronic trading platform operator, e-commerce, e-commerce operator, e-commerce entities.*

Introduction

In the context of both global and local economic relations, e-commerce (or "e-tijorat" in Uzbek) - conducting trade and commercial activities over the internet

- is gaining significant importance. E-commerce is defined as the buying and selling of goods (services, products) within the framework of entrepreneurial activity using information systems, according to the terms of a contract concluded through an electronic trading platform. State and corporate purchases within the scope of e-commerce are organized and conducted in accordance with the procedure established by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On ELECTRONIC COMMERCE" was adopted by the Legislative Chamber on June 21, 2022, and approved by the Senate on September 13, 2022. Ushbu

The law uses the following main concepts:

Digital products: Electronic copies of intellectual property objects (digital goods), as well as performing specific actions or activities in the digital information environment that do not have material results, including obtaining "cloud technologies" (digital services) and subscribing to them.

Electronic trading platform: An information system that enables distance buying and selling of goods (services, products).

Operator of electronic trading platform: A legal entity providing services of an electronic trading platform to participants of electronic commerce.

Electronic commerce: The sale and purchase of goods (services, products) within the framework of entrepreneurial activity using information systems, according to the terms of an agreement concluded through an electronic trading platform.

Electronic commerce operator: A legal entity providing services related to the circulation of electronic documents and electronic messages in electronic commerce.

Subjects of electronic commerce: Participants of electronic commerce and/or operators of electronic commerce.

The "Law on Electronic Commerce" protects the rights and interests of both users and entrepreneurs, establishing a system for ensuring responsibility for conducting electronic transactions and for violations of rights. Legal regulations and payment systems play a crucial role in creating a reliable and sustainable ecosystem for electronic commerce. They ensure the protection of the rights and interests of all participants in the process - both buyers and sellers.

The National Registry of Electronic Commerce Subjects is a single electronic database established by the decree PQ-3724 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2018, on measures to accelerate the

development of electronic commerce. This registry contains information about local subjects of electronic commerce and serves as a centralized electronic bank of information.

The main tasks and directions of the National Registry of Electronic Commerce Subjects are as follows:

Establishing a Single Electronic Bank: Creating a centralized electronic database to gather information about participants in electronic commerce.

Monitoring and Evaluating the Current State of Electronic Commerce: Assessing the efficiency of information systems and resources in current electronic commerce operations.

Preparing Analytical Reviews and Recommendations: Conducting purposeful analysis and preparing recommendations for improving existing legislation to promote the effective development of electronic commerce.

According to the decree PQ-3724 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2018, on measures to accelerate the development of electronic commerce, the National Registry is established under the Ministry for Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan to develop, maintain, and improve the National Registry. Legal entities and private entrepreneurs registered in the National Registry are subject to a single tax payment of 2% of the base rate.

Research methodology

It is based on scientific abstraction, observation, comparison.

Analysis of Literature on the Topic

The history of digital economy and e-commerce has been enriched by extensive scientific and technological research. In 1961, Leonard Kleinrock from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology developed the theory of packet switching for information exchange. In 1962, J.C.R. Licklider from the United States published the "Galactic Network," foreseeing the future existence of a global computer network, which would provide immediate access to programs and databases from any point in the world. His prediction laid the foundation for the modern Internet. In 1993, Dutch mathematician David Chaum invented mechanisms for implementing electronic cash transactions. On October 13, 1994, Mark Andreessen and James Clark unveiled the new Netscape web browser. Netscape expanded the possibilities of electronic commerce and dominated a large portion of the software products market. In the same year, Stanford University students Jerry Yang and David Filo created the Yahoo! Internet resource directory. The day their shares were issued for trading (April

12, 1996), their price reached \$33, with a nominal price of \$12. Currently, Yahoo! has a market capitalization of tens of billions of dollars. On September 7, 1998, Sergey Brin and Larry Page, graduates of Stanford University, created the Google search engine. Today, Google employees from 15 countries live in 5,000 countries. Google handles over 200 million searches in 80 languages every day. Before the 2008-2010 crisis, the company's market capitalization exceeded \$180 billion.

Kobelev O. A. defines "e-commerce" as entrepreneurial activity in conducting trade operations using electronic information exchange tools.

In our country, scientists such as S.S. Gulomov, I.S. Abdullayev, R.H. Ayupov, G.R. Boltaboeva, and others are conducting systematic scientific research on optimization issues, as well as on digital economy and blockchain technologies.

Materials and methods

Electronic commerce offers numerous advantages and benefits, including:

- Increased Speed of Information Retrieval in International Transactions: With electronic commerce, obtaining information in international transactions becomes faster.

- Reduced Production and Sales Cycle: The time required for production and sales is shortened through electronic commerce.

- Lower Communication Costs: Electronic commerce reduces communication costs compared to traditional methods.

Companies can establish open communication with consumers through efficient use of information technologies, providing quick information to partners and customers about products and services. It also offers alternative sales channels, such as opening and creating electronic stores on trading websites.

In Uzbekistan, government agencies are following several principles widely used in international practice to develop electronic commerce:

- The active role of the corporate sector is essential in developing electronic commerce;
- Various barriers not based on corporate sector must not be imposed on electronic commerce;
- Government authorities may intervene in electronic commerce processes to support and improve the legal framework and to support entities in this field;
- When developing regulations for managing electronic commerce, government authorities must consider the unique features of the Internet;

- Electronic commerce processes should occur on a global scale, without being divided administratively and territorially, and without being subject to state boundaries and borders.

Analysis and results

In this way, it is necessary to emphasize that the opportunities for developing e-commerce in Uzbekistan are increasing year by year. Its development creates new markets and opportunities to find new customers for our national producers. Choosing the right path for developing e-commerce will not only contribute to the prosperity of our people and the progress of our society but will also have a positive impact on our economic development, aligning Uzbekistan with one of the leading representatives of the global market in the future.

Conclusions and suggestions:

In addressing the aforementioned challenges, the following areas should be prioritized:

- Enhancing Scientific Research in E-commerce: Deepening scientific research in the field of e-commerce is essential. This involves conducting research, writing articles, creating specialized internet resources, organizing regular forums and conferences, and considering not only the technical but also the economic and legal aspects of e-commerce. Addressing this key challenge will help to improve the training of skilled personnel.

- Promoting Competition in Telecommunication Services: Developing competition in providing telecommunication services leads to an increase in service quality, a decrease in prices, and the creation of specific internet audiences for e-commerce.

- Ensuring the Continuous Availability of Favorable Legal Conditions for Investment in ICT: It is crucial to ensure that convenient legal conditions for investment in the ICT sector are consistently maintained.

- Establishing Self-Regulation and Exchange of Experience Systems: Creating self-regulation and experience exchange systems will facilitate the sharing of knowledge and best practices among e-commerce participants.

- Developing the E-learning System for E-commerce: Enhancing the e-learning system for e-commerce will contribute to the training and development of professionals in this field.

- Promoting Nationwide Expansion of Information Technologies: Ensuring the widespread adoption of information technologies throughout Uzbekistan,

not only in regional centers but also in remote rural areas, will significantly contribute to the visible growth of e-commerce.

- Efficient Implementation of Online Banking Systems: Implementing online banking systems nationwide will enhance the ability of entrepreneurs engaged in various sectors to conduct free trade with their goods and services via the internet. Additionally, this will lead to significant changes in other areas of the banking sector.

These measures will play a crucial role in addressing the challenges and further advancing the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan.

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